

Creating a new Wikidata taxon item

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[Search for taxon item](#)

[Manually creating a taxon item](#)

[Instance of](#)

[Taxon name](#)

[Taxon rank](#)

[Parent taxon](#)

[Data model for a taxon Wikidata item](#)

[Other statements](#)

Search for taxon item

When creating a new Wikidata taxon item, FIRST search Wikidata for that taxon. Creating duplicate items is discouraged and searching for the taxon item will reduce the risk of this occurring.

The screenshot shows the Wikidata search interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Paracroria niger' and a 'Search' button. Below the search bar, there is a dropdown menu with the text 'Search for pages containing Paracroria niger'. The main heading is 'Search results'. Below this, there is a text box with the instruction: 'To search for Wikidata items by their title on a given site, use [Special:ItemByTitle](#).' Below this, there is another search bar with the text 'Paracroria niger' and a 'Search' button. Below the search bar, there is a dropdown menu with the text 'Advanced search: Sort by relevance'. Below this, there is a dropdown menu with the text 'Search in: (Main)'. At the bottom, there is a message: 'There were no results matching the query. You may [create a new item](#) for "Paracroria niger".'

Screenshot of search of Wikidata items for the newly described Mali moth species *Paracroria niger*. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Manually creating a taxon item

Once satisfied that the taxon item does not exist, it can be manually created by going to the main page of Wikidata https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata:Main_Page. On the left hand side of that page is the main menu. The fourth option down gives the editor a link to click to create a new item. Press that link.

Screenshot of Wikidata. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/)

This will take the editor to the “Create a new Item” form. Relevant fields in that form should be filled out and then the item can be created.

Create a new Item

Please make sure that the item you want to create complies with our [notability policy](#) and that [it doesn't already exist](#).

If you want to create an item about a [living person](#), be mindful of their privacy.

We appreciate it if you create a [label](#) and a [description](#) for all of your new items.

The first letter of your label should only be capitalized if it is a [proper noun \(Q147276\)](#), and your description should *not* be phrased as a sentence.

To create a new lexeme ([read here first to learn how a lexeme is different from an item](#)), please use [Special:NewLexeme](#).

By clicking "Create", you agree to the [terms of use](#), and you irrevocably agree to release your contribution under the [Creative Commons CC0 License](#).

Create a new Item

Language:
 ▼

Label:

Description:

Aliases, pipe-separated:

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Label

It is recommended that the label of the item be the taxon name as the Wikidata item relates to a taxonomic concept. Some taxon items in Wikidata have the main label as the common name for the species. However this can result in confusion as the common name may apply to multiple species or alternatively the common name may apply to both the current taxonomic name as well as taxonomic synonyms, that is the taxonomic name the species, genus or family was previously known as.

Description

The description of the item should be a brief description of the taxon. For example “species of moth” or “genus of fungi”.

Aliases

The aliases section is where to add common names and abbreviations can be added.

Taxonomic synonyms should **NOT** be added to the aliases section. Instead, each taxonomic synonym should have its own Wikidata item. Those synonym items can then be linked to other taxon Wikidata items via statements using the properties “taxon synonym of” ([P12763](#)) (see example [Q10398706](#)) and “taxon synonym” ([P1420](#)) (see example [Q13705567](#)).

Create item

Once the editor is satisfied that all the necessary information has been added to the Create a new Item form, the item can be created by pressing the blue “create” button.

Create a new Item

Language:

en ▼

Label:

Paracroria niger

Description:

species of moth found in Mali

Aliases, pipe-separated:

P|niger

Create

Screenshot of Wikidata. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Enrich item

The item can now be enriched with data about the taxon.

Descriptions and aliases

Where the editor speaks languages other than English they are encouraged to add a description of the item and aliases for that taxon name in that language. Editors are also encouraged to undertake this enrichment on existing taxon items. In the example below another editor has added a description of this taxon in Arabic.

Paracroria niger (Q136396258)...

[Item](#) [Discussion](#) [Read](#) [View](#) [View history](#) [★](#) [Page](#) [Copy QID](#)

species of moth found in Mali [edit](#)

P. niger

▸ [Recoin: Most relevant properties which are absent](#)

▾ [In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
default for all languages	No label defined	–	
English	Paracroria niger by Ambrosia10	species of moth found in Mali by Ambrosia10	P. niger by Ambrosia10
Arabic	No label defined		نوع من الحشرات

Screenshot of Wikidata. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Instance of

Statements should be added to the newly created item to add data about the taxon. The first statement for a new taxon item should always be an “instance of” statement stating the Wikidata item is an instance of a taxon. This statement should also be referenced. To add the “instance of” statement click “+ add statement” under the “Statements” section. Move the cursor to the property box on the left hand side and select “instance of”. Then move the cursor to the right hand side box and type “taxon”.

Paracroria niger (Q136396258)...

[Item](#) [Discussion](#) [Read](#) [View](#) [View history](#) [★](#) [Page](#) ▼

species of moth found in Mali [edit](#)

P. niger

[▶ Reconcil: Most relevant properties which are absent](#)

[▶ In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
default for all languages	No label defined	–	
English	Paracroria niger by Ambrosia10	species of moth found in Mali by Ambrosia10	P. niger by Ambrosia10

Statements [edit](#)

instance of
type to which this subject corresponds/belongs. Different from P279 (subclass of); for example: K2 is an instance of mountain; volcano is a subclass of mountain

subclass of
this item is a subclass (subset) of that item; ALL instances of this item are instances of that item; different from P31 (instance of), e.g.: volcano is a subclass of mountain; Everest is an instance of mountain

[▶ 0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

Screenshot of Wikidata. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

In the example below the reference added is a link to the Wikidata item for the publication that described this species. However other appropriate references could be a reference to taxonomic databases such as the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) or a website URL linking to an appropriate source. Where a website URL is added for the reference the appropriate property to use is “reference URL” ([P854](#)).

Statements [edit](#)

✓ publish ✕ cancel ?

[+ add qualifier](#)

[▶ 1 reference](#)

[remove](#)

[+ add](#)

[+ add reference](#)

Screenshot of Wikidata. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Once an “instance of” statement has been added and the item is refreshed, Wikidata will then suggest other statements that may be appropriate to add to the item via the property dropdown menu.

Statements

[instance of](#) taxon [edit](#)

[1 reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

Property publish cancel ?

- taxon name**
correct scientific name of a taxon (according to the reference given)
- taxon rank**
level in a taxonomic hierarchy
- parent taxon**
closest parent taxon of the taxon in question
- GBIF taxon ID**
taxon identifier in GBIF
- short name**
short name of a place, organisation, person, journal, Wikidata property, etc. Used by some Wikipedia templates.
- Catalogue of Life ID**
identifier of a taxon or synonym in the Catalogue of Life
- Open Tree of Life ID**
identifier for an entity in Open Tree of Life, a comprehensive, dynamic and digitally-available tree of life by synthesizing published phylogenetic trees along with taxonomic data

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For taxon items the minimum required statements that should be added include the taxon name, the taxon rank and the parent taxon statements.

Taxon name

A taxon name statement should be added to the item. This name should be the same as the label of the item

[taxon name](#) publish remove cancel ?

[by Ambrosia10](#) Paracrororia niger

[+ add qualifier](#)

[- 0 references](#)

[+ add reference](#)

[+ add value](#)

When adding the taxon name statement, qualifiers can be added to that statement. First the taxon authors should be added as qualifiers to the taxon name statement. This links to Wikidata items for the authors of that taxon name. Second, the year of publication of scientific name for the taxon should also be added.

[taxon name](#) publish cancel ?

[Paracrororia niger](#)

- [taxon author](#) Aidas Saldaitis remove
- [taxon author](#) Alexey M. Prozorov remove
- [taxon author](#) Gunter C. Muller remove
- [year of publication of scier](#) Günter C. Müller entomologist remove

[+ add qualifier](#)

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This statement should also be referenced. If the reference used is a publication giving the first description of the species, a statement can be added to the reference explaining that the “reference has role” ([P6184](#)) of “first valid description” ([Q1361864](#)). There are other “reference has role” values that can be added depending on the type of reference. A full list is set out in the Taxon Item Properties figure on page 9 of this document.

taxon name: Paracroria niger

taxon author: Aidas Saldaitis

taxon author: Alexey M. Prozorov

taxon author: Günter C. Müller

year of publication of scier: 2025

1 reference

stated in: Notes on the African genus *Paracroria* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), with three new species descriptions

reference has role: first valid description

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Taxon rank

The taxon rank of the taxon should then be added to the Wikidata item. In the example given below, the taxon rank is species. Again this statement should be referenced.

taxon rank: species

species
one of the basic units of biological classification and a taxonomic rank

subspecies
taxonomic rank subordinate to species. Subspecies differentiate closely related organisms within a single species

Wikispecies (*Species.wikimedia.org*)
free multilingual online species directory

Index Fungorum (*Species Fungorum*)
international project to index all formal (scientific) names in the kingdom of Fungi

species nova
phrase used when publishing the name of a new species

Screenshot of Wikidata. Wikimedia Foundation. [CC BY-SA 4.0](#)

Parent taxon

The parent taxon Wikidata item should be added. In the below example, as the species is *Paracroria niger*, the parent taxon is the genus *Paracroria*. This statement should again be referenced. It is acceptable to use the same reference for all appropriate statements given in the item, so long as the reference supports those statements.

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Data model for a taxon Wikidata item

Label: Taxon item name

Description: Description of taxon e.g. species of moth, genus of fungi etc

Minimum required statements:

[P31](#) instance of [Q16521](#) taxon

[P225](#) taxon name [string of taxon name]

Qualifier to statement [P405](#) taxon author [Qitem for Author/s]

[P574](#) year of taxon publication [string of year]

(If needed) [P3831](#) object of statement has role [Q14594740](#) recombination

Referencing taxon name statement:

If you are using the publication that gives the first description of the taxon as a reference for the above taxon name or qualifiers this statement should be structured as follows:

P248 stated in	[Qitem for first description publication]
P304 page(s)	[string for page number/s in the publication where first description can be found]
P6184 reference has role	Q1361864 first description
If available	
P687 BHL page id	[number string of BHL page id]

For taxon items that are recombinations follow the advice given here:

https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Wikidata_talk:WikiProject_Taxonomy/Archive/2021/10#h-Guidelines_for_adding_references_for_taxonomic_names-2021-08-11T14:58:00.000Z

[P105](#) taxon rank [Q7432](#) species, [Q34740](#) genus

[P171](#) parent taxon [Qitem for genus]

Other statements

There are many other types of statements that can be added to a Wikidata taxon item. Just some properties that have been used to enrich taxa items are shown in the diagram below.

Taxon item properties diagram by Siobhan Leachman and Heidi Meudt, [CC0](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Taxon_item_properties_diagram_pdf.pdf), via Wikimedia Commons https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Taxon_item_properties_diagram_pdf.pdf

Images

One important statement that can also be added to the Wikidata item is a link to an image of the taxon. This statement will link the Wikidata item for the taxon to an image of the taxon sourced from Wikimedia Commons https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/Main_Page. It is possible to add multiple images statements. These may include images of the life stages of the species, images of the male and female of the organism or images of the significant parts of the organism, for example, leaf, seed, flower and so on.

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Example data model for adding insect images to Wikidata taxon items

[P18](#) image

- adult female image
- adult male image
- pupa image
- larvae image
- egg image

Qualifier statement for adult images [P21](#) sex or gender [Q43445](#) female organism
[Q44148](#) male organism

Qualifier statement for images [P180](#) depicts [Q80994](#) adult
[Q129270](#) larva
[Q170595](#) pupa
[Q3594109](#) insect egg